

Supplementary Figure 1

Supplementary Fig. 1. RT-qPCR analysis demonstrated increased expression of MMP3 ($p < 0.001$) and MMP9 ($p < 0.001$), but not MMP2 and MMP14 after IL-1 β stimulation. MMP2 and MMP14 were constitutively expressed in astrocytes and their expression did not change after IL-1 β stimulation, whereas MMP3 expression was induced from low expression to a level comparable with that of MMP2. MMP9 was induced, but was not highly expressed relative to the other MMPs. The data represented as normalized NO value, which is inversely proportional to Ct value and represents estimated starting amount of mRNA in the sample (see Materials and Methods for more information).